

ECONOMETRIC APPROACHES TO EVALUATING VECTOR AUTOREGRESSIVE AND AUTOREGRESSIVE DISTRIBUTED LAG MODELS IN EMERGING ECONOMIES

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Abstract

This study evaluates the performance of Vector Autoregressive (VAR) and Autoregressive Distributed lag (ARDL) Models in analyzing econometric relationships, specifically focusing on the interaction of some macroeconomic indicators in Nigeria. The variables used are inflation, exchange rate, crude oil price, and imports with data from central Bank of Nigeria statistical data base from January, 1995 to March, 2024. Methods utilized are the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) and Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. Output from the analysis reveal that the VAR model demonstrates superior performance, capturing complex, simultaneous lags. It achieves a high explanatory fit of R^2 - 0.978. In contrast, the ARDL model adopts a more restrictive exogenous framework with simplified lag structure, resulting in lower explanatory power of 21 %. Furthermore, while both models identify a significant relationship between COP and EXR, the VAR model identifies a more pronounced impact (29.11). Findings propose that for the data set analyzed, the VAR framework provides a more robust and comprehensive understanding of the variables' dynamic interactions. Prioritizing, the VAR over ARDL to describe the relationship between crude oil price and exchange rate is recommended since short-run relationship exist among the variables, policy makers should focus on tactical, immediate interventions rather than relying on long-term structural shifts.

Keywords: Econometric, Macroeconomic, Dynamic, Vector, Autoregressive, Model.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the Nigerian economy has faced significant volatility driven by its dependence on external sector and fluctuations in global commodity prices (Ekpo, 2023). Understanding the interplay between macroeconomic indicators, such as inflation, exchange rate, crude oil price, and imports, requires an analytical framework that accounts for both the relative structure of the economy and the lag effects inherent in policy transmission. Recent empirical evidence reveal that lag effects are crucial in the Nigerian context. For instance, studies on monetary policy pass-through indicate that while certain channels, like exchange rate, is influential, others, such as credit transmission, may be ineffectual or subject to significant time delays. Ejukwa (2023) cited that the disequilibrium in endogenous variable and uncertainty in macroeconomic pointers are the shocks that are responsible for economic instability. Econometric modeling in Nigeria frequently uses vector autoregression (VAR) and Autoregressive Distributed Lag

(ARDL) techniques to capture these dynamics. By treating all variables as endogenous, the VAR model is particularly effective for assessing the relative structure of shocks, allowing researchers to observe how a shock in one variable propagates through others over time (Mihai et al., 2024). However, the Autoregressive Distributed Lag approach introduced by Pesaran et al. (2001) has become a preferred method for identifying long-run relationships and short-run lag effects when different orders of variables are integrated. Nwuju et al. (2024) model the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on economic growth and stability in Nigeria using the vector autoregressive (VAR) and autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) models. They found no long-run relationship, and ARDL was the preferred model to VAR. Usmana and Osagie (2023) employed ARDL and VAR on gross domestic product, exchange rate, interest rate, and unemployment in Nigeria. Shaibu and Osamwoyi (2020) developed a multivariate autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model and a univariate autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) model for inflation, exchange rate interest rate, and broad money supply. They found that Nigeria's inflation is largely driven by the interest rate, exchange rate, and broad money supply. Existing empirical studies on Nigeria have largely applied VAR, ARDL, VECM, or ARIMA models to examine the relationship between inflation, exchange rate, interest rate, GDP, unemployment, and money supply. However, a notable gap exists in the literature regarding the joint and comparative application of VAR and ARDL models to assess the dynamics and short-run effects of key external sector variables, such as crude oil price and imports, on inflation and exchange rate in Nigeria.

Scope of the study

The scope of this study is limited to the vector autoregressive (VAR) and autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) models. The paper recognizes four metrics from January 1995 to March 2024: inflation, exchange rate, crude oil price, and imports.

Aim and Objectives:

This study aims to model the interaction among macroeconomic indicators using VAR and ARDL models and investigate the causation among crude oil price, exchange rate, imports, and inflation in Nigeria. The objectives are as follows:

- i. The historical trends and patterns of the variables are examined to understand their evolution over time.
- ii. Evaluate the short-run dynamics for the VAR and ARDL models.
- iii. Compare the performance of VAR and ARDL to determine the model with the best fit and generate more accurate estimates of the relationship between the variables.

2. Materials and Methods

Research Design

The overall plan or blueprint that guided the research process. Kerlinger (1986) explained that a research design is a blueprint or plan that guides the researcher's investigation and analysis in finding answers to research questions. This study used an ex-post facto research design. This means that the researcher could not control how the data turned out.

Source and Type of Data

Data for this research were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Database website. The data used were monthly inflation rate, exchange rate, import, and crude oil price data for Nigeria from January 1995 to March 2024.

Preliminary Investigation

Data Cleaning

This is done to handle any missing values using methods such as mean/median imputation, regression imputation, or time-series-specific methods. In addition, the data are transformed if necessary to stabilize variance or remove nonlinearity. Common transformations include logarithmic, square root or Box-Cox transformation.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics such as the mean, median, mode, range, variance, standard deviation, and others are often used to get a feel of the data before conducting more in-depth analysis. Inferential statistics, which helps to determine whether a data set follows a normal distribution and can inform further statistical analysis, were also conducted. The normality test is performed using the Jarque-Bera test statistics developed by Jarque and Bera (1980) but popularized by Ejukwa et al. (2025) and is defined as follows:

$$X^2 = \frac{N}{6} \left[S^2 + \frac{(K-3)^2}{4} \right] \quad (1)$$

Where S represents skewness, K represents kurtosis, and N represents the size of the macroeconomic variables used.

Time Plot

A time plot, also known as a time series plot, is a graphical representation of data points collected over time. The values of the variables are displayed on the y-axis and time on the x-axis. Time plots are commonly used to identify data trends, patterns, outliers, and seasonal variations.

Unit Root

A unit root indicates non-stationarity in a time series, and identifying this characteristic is essential for accurate modeling, as noted by Biu et al. (2012). The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and the Phillip-Perron test (PPT) are the most common methods for detecting unit root. Both test use the null hypothesis that a unit root exists. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller method (Dickey-Fuller, 1981) is utilized to assess stationarity in this study.

$$\Delta x_{i,t} = Kx_{i,t-1} + \sum_{k=1}^n \beta_{i,k} \Delta x_{i,t-k} + \varepsilon_{k,t} \quad (2)$$

Where,

$\Delta x_{i,t}$ = the 1st difference value of x

$Kx_{i,t-1}$ = the 1st lagged value of x

$\sum_{k=1}^n \beta_{i,k} \Delta x_{i,t-k}$ = the nth lag of 1st difference value of x

$\varepsilon_{k,t}$ = the error term

Vector autoregressive (VAR) model

VAR is a flexible and simple model for multivariate time series data with autoregressive characteristics that can be used for data description, estimation, and forecasting. The model treats all variables as endogenous and expresses each variable as dependent on its lag value and other variables' lagged values. The stationarity of data is crucial for VAR modeling, and the order of integration is determined if the time series is non-stationary. The error terms in VAR modeling must be normal and independent (Suharsono, 2017).

A VAR model is given as follows:

$$Y_t = C + A_1Y_{t-1} + A_2Y_{t-2} + \dots + A_pY_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Where;

$Y_t = (y_{1t}, y_{2t}, \dots)$ is an $(n \times n)$ vector time series variable.

$A = (n \times n)$ coefficient matrices.

$\varepsilon_t =$ is an $(n \times 1)$ is an unobserved zero mean error term.

The model can be represented as a matrix as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} y_{1t} \\ y_{2t} \\ \vdots \\ y_{nt} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \\ \vdots \\ c_n \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} A_{11}^1 & A_{12}^1 & \dots & A_{1n}^1 \\ A_{21}^1 & A_{22}^1 & \dots & A_{2n}^1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ A_{n1}^1 & A_{n2}^1 & \dots & A_{nn}^1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} y_{1t-1} \\ y_{2t-1} \\ \vdots \\ y_{nt-1} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} A_{11}^2 & A_{12}^2 & \dots & A_{1n}^2 \\ A_{21}^2 & A_{22}^2 & \dots & A_{2n}^2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ A_{n1}^2 & A_{n2}^2 & \dots & A_{nn}^2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} y_{1t-2} \\ y_{2t-2} \\ \vdots \\ y_{nt-2} \end{pmatrix} + \dots + \begin{pmatrix} A_{11}^p & A_{12}^p & \dots & A_{1n}^p \\ A_{21}^p & A_{22}^p & \dots & A_{2n}^p \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ A_{n1}^p & A_{n2}^p & \dots & A_{nn}^p \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} y_{1t-p} \\ y_{2t-p} \\ \vdots \\ y_{nt-p} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{1t} \\ \varepsilon_{2t} \\ \vdots \\ \varepsilon_{nt} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The general vector autoregressive model of order k for the four variables (COP, EXR, INF, and IMP) is specified as follows:

$$COP = \alpha_1 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i COP_{t-i} + \sum_{m=1}^k \varphi_m EXR + \sum_{n=1}^k \vartheta_n INF_{t-n} + \sum_{p=1}^k \varsigma_p IMP_{t-p} + u_{1t} \quad (5)$$

$$EXR = \alpha_2 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i COP_{t-i} + \sum_{m=1}^k \varphi_m EXR + \sum_{n=1}^k \vartheta_n INF_{t-n} + \sum_{p=1}^k \varsigma_p IMP_{t-p} + u_{2t} \quad (6)$$

$$INF = \alpha_3 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i COP_{t-i} + \sum_{m=1}^k \varphi_m EXR + \sum_{n=1}^k \vartheta_n INF_{t-n} + \sum_{p=1}^k \varsigma_p IMP_{t-p} + u_{3t} \quad (7)$$

$$IMP = \alpha_4 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i COP_{t-i} + \sum_{m=1}^k \varphi_m EXR + \sum_{n=1}^k \vartheta_n INF_{t-n} + \sum_{p=1}^k \varsigma_p IMP_{t-p} + u_{4t} \quad (8)$$

Where

COP- crude oil price; EXR - exchange rate; INF- inflation rate

IMP- imports; the $\alpha_1 - \alpha_4$ constant terms for the four variables

$u_{1t} - u_{4t}$ - Error Terms.

Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model

To apply the ARDL technique introduced by Pesaran and Shin (1998) and popularized by Ejukwa et al. (2023), the underlying variables must be a combination of I(0) and I(1) or I(1) alone. This helps avoid the

pretesting problems associated with standard co-integration analysis, which requires the classification of the variables into I (0) and I (1). If the trace, Max eigenvalue, or F-statistics establishes a single long-run relationship, the ARDL approach can be applied rather than the Johansen and Juselius approach (Ejukwa et al., 2023).

The ARDL model equation with four variables can be represented as follows:

$$\Delta COP_t = \sigma_1 + \sum_{t-1}^k \phi_1 \Delta COP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-1}^k \theta_1 \Delta EXR_{t-1} + \sum_{t-1}^k \vartheta_1 \Delta INF_{t-1} + \sum_{t-1}^k \alpha_1 \Delta IMP_{t-1} + \pi_{1,t} \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta EXR_t = \sigma_2 + \sum_{t-1}^k \phi_2 \Delta EXR_{t-1} + \sum_{t-1}^k \theta_2 \Delta INF_{t-1} + \sum_{t-1}^k \vartheta_2 \Delta IMP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-1}^k \alpha_2 \Delta COP_{t-1} + \pi_{2,t} \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta INF_t = \sigma_3 + \sum_{t-1}^k \phi_3 \Delta INF_{t-1} + \sum_{t-1}^k \theta_3 \Delta EXR_{t-1} + \sum_{t-1}^k \vartheta_3 \Delta COP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-1}^k \alpha_3 \Delta EXR_{t-1} + \pi_{3,t} \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta IMP_t = \sigma_4 + \sum_{t-1}^k \phi_4 \Delta IMP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-1}^k \theta_4 \Delta COP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-1}^k \vartheta_4 \Delta EXR_{t-1} + \sum_{t-1}^k \alpha_4 \Delta INF_{t-1} + \pi_{4,t} \quad (12)$$

Where,

σ_1 - Constant, ϕ , θ , α , ϑ - Short run coefficients, π - Shock, Δ - Difference operator

COP - crude oil price; EXR - exchange rate; INF - inflation; IMP, import

Lag Order Selection

Lag length is a crucial factor in specifying a VAR model. It determines the number of past observations of each variable used to predict its current value. The Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) was used to determine the optimal lag length.

Akaike Information Criteria

A major reason for using AIC is to avoid model overfitting.

$$AIC = -2 \ln(L) + 2k \quad (13)$$

Where k is the number of independent variables and L is the log-likelihood estimator.

Johansen cointegration and ARDL bounds test

While individual time series may exhibit random walk behavior, a linear combination of these variables may be stationary. This reveals that the variables tend to move together in the long run despite short-term fluctuations. The Johansen cointegration test and the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) bounds test are two prominent methods for testing for cointegration. The Johansen test is a multivariate method that examines the co-integrating rank of a system of variables and does not allow for a mixed order of integration. The trace statistic and the maximum eigenvalue statistic are the two primary test statistics.

$$\lambda_{\text{Trace}} = -T \sum_{t=r+1}^n \ln(1 - \lambda_i)$$

For $i = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$

$$\lambda_{\text{Max}} = -T \ln(1 - \lambda_r + 1)$$

However, the ARDL bounds test is a relatively recent method for testing co-integration and is particularly useful when dealing with a mixed order of integration. The hypothesis is stated as follows:

$H_0: \lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = 0$ (no long-term relationship exists)

$H_1: \lambda_1 \neq \lambda_2 \neq \lambda_3 \neq 0$ (exists a long-run relationship)

Model Estimation

Ordinary least squares (OLS) estimation

The OLS method is a statistical technique used to determine the optimal “line of best fit” for a data set. To attain this, it minimizes the sum of squared differences (residuals) between the observed data points and the values predicted by the model equation.

AR (1) estimation

Let (x_t) be a covariance – stationary process defined by the fundamental representation $(\phi < 1)$.

$$X_t = \phi_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \tag{14}$$

Where (ε_t) is the innovation process of (x_t)

The ordinary least squares estimation of ϕ is defined in Equation 13 as follows:

$$\hat{\phi}_{ols} = \left(\sum_{t=1}^T x_{t-1}^2 \right)^{-1} \left(\sum_{t=2}^T x_{t-1} x_t \right) \tag{15}$$

MA (1) estimation

Let (x_t) be a stationary covariance process defined by the representation $(\theta < 1)$

$$X_t = \varepsilon_t + \theta \varepsilon_{t-1} \tag{16}$$

Where (ε_t) is the innovation process of (x_t) .

Post Estimation

After estimating a model, it is important to check the reliability of the results. To ensure the reliability of the findings, several diagnostic measures were employed, such as the Breusch-Godfrey LM test for serial correlation, heteroscedasticity test for variance consistency, inverse root of the AR characteristic polynomial, and the cumulative sum test for structural stability. These diagnostics are essential because, as noted by Ejukwa et al. (2023), standard regression models operate on the assumption that error terms are distributed independently and identically (i.i.d). Furthermore, Shrestha et al. (2018) emphasized the role of stability diagnostics in verifying that model parameters remain constant throughout the data set. The serial correlation LM test determines whether prediction errors for a specific variable are influenced by errors from previous periods.

3. Results

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on INF, EXR, IMP, and COP

Statistics	COP	EXR	IMP
Mean	60.18777	28476.16	79.99460
Median	57.55000	33059.30	70.72000
Maximum	138.7400	62081.86	163.4283
Minimum	10.22000	1002.952	14.28000
Std.Dev.	34.36579	16918.48	35.85728
Skewness	0.359885	-0.241540	0.516767
Kurtosis	1.930128	1.644923	2.142557

Jarque-Bera	24.17837	30.09544	26.22449
Probability	0.000006	0.000000	0.000002
Sum	21005.53	9938181.	27918.12
Sum Sq.Dev.	410990.6	9.96E+10	447439.0
Observations	349	349	349

COP: Crude Oil Price, EXR: Exchange Rate, IMP: Import, INF: Inflation Rate

Figure 1: Historical behavior of the raw series for EXR, COP, INF, and IMP

Figure 2: Historical pattern of the difference series for EXR, COP, INF, and IMP

Table 2: Unit Root Test Results for INF, EXR, IMP, and COP

VAR	Level			First Difference					Remark
	ADFT	C.V 5%	PPT	C.V 5%	ADFT	C.V 5%	PPT	C.V 5%	
INF	-9.3888	-3.4492 (0.0000**)	-20.630	-2.869629 (0.0000**)	-	-	-	-	I(0)
EXR	-0.9272	-2.8697 (0.7789)	-1.3717	-2.8696 (0.5965)	-9.1705	-2.8697 (0.0000**)	-16.3690	-2.8696 (0.0000**)	I(1)
IMP	-1.697	-2.869 (0.4829)	-1.264	-2.869 (0.6472)	-11.269	-2.870 (0.000**)	-14.532	-2.869 (0.000**)	I(1)
COP	-1.733	-2.869 (0.4134)	-1.788	-2.869 (0.3859)	-11.082	-2.869 (0.000**)	-13.450	-2.869 (0.000**)	I(1)

Footnote: **= significant at 5%

ADFT: Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test, C.V: Critical Value, PPT: Phillip Perron Test

Table 3: Results for lag order selection for the VAR model

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-8390.618	NA	5.09e+16	49.819	49.865	49.837
1	-6058.260	4595.507	5.45e+10	36.072	36.299	36.163
2	-6008.967	95.952	4.47e+10	35.875	36.285*	36.038*
3	-5991.351	33.872*	4.43e+1*	35.866*	36.455	36.101
4	-5980.800	20.039	4.58e+10	35.898	36.669	36.205
5	-5972.816	14.973	4.80e+10	35.945	36.898	36.325
6	-5967.274	10.261	5.11e+10	36.008	37.141	36.459

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at the 5% level)

FPE: Final prediction error

AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion

HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

Table 4: Results of the Johansen cointegration test

Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None	0.034117	25.19910	47.85613	0.9133
At most 1	0.028664	13.36222	29.79707	0.8744
At most 2	0.009933	3.445076	15.49471	0.9431
At most 3	0.000120	0.041037	3.841466	0.8394

Trace test indicates no cointegration at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

Table 5: Results of VAR estimation

	INF	EXR	COP	IMP
INF(-1)	0.924373* (0.05471) [16.8973]	14.83993 (13.0765) [1.13486]	0.031095 (0.06826) [0.45554]	0.066343 (0.07173) [0.92494]
INF(-2)	-0.055451 (0.07466) [-0.74276]	0.275291 (17.8453) [0.01543]	-0.090222 (0.09315) [-0.96855]	0.050677 (0.09789) [0.51772]
INF(-3)	0.125604* (0.05512) [2.27877]	-13.22419 (13.1754) [-1.00371]	0.059558 (0.06877) [0.86600]	-0.090829 (0.07227) [-1.25680]
EXR(-1)	0.000343 (0.00022) [1.55643]	1.160084* (0.05265) [22.0334]	-2.02E-05 (0.00027) [-0.07345]	0.000212 (0.00029) [0.73257]
EXR(-2)	-0.000466 (0.00033) [-1.41213]	0.098285 (0.07884) [1.24658]	0.000294 (0.00041) [0.71517]	0.000361 (0.00043) [0.83495]
EXR(-3)	0.000155	-0.273787*	-0.000223	-0.000486

	(0.00021) [0.74447]	(0.04974) [-5.50462]	(0.00026) [-0.85911]	(0.00027) [-1.78098]
COP(-1)	-0.015211 (0.04470) [-0.34027]	29.11467* (10.6853) [2.72474]	1.266221* (0.05578) [22.7017]	0.011374 (0.05861) [0.19405]
COP(-2)	0.023773 (0.07014) [0.33892]	-20.75582 (16.7666) [-1.23793]	-0.344433 (0.08752) [-3.93547]	0.048191 (0.09197) [0.52399]
COP(-3)	-0.009692 (0.04573) [-0.21195]	-3.969557 (10.9304) [-0.36317]	0.032398 (0.05706) [0.56784]	-0.089878 (0.05996) [-1.49908]
IMP(-1)	-0.031874 (0.04193) [-0.76011]	-14.03842 (10.0235) [-1.40055]	-0.066251 (0.05232) [-1.26623]	1.187856* (0.05498) [21.6048]
IMP(-2)	0.074603 (0.06432) [1.15994]	13.63620 (15.3738) [0.88698]	0.091494 (0.08025) [1.14011]	-0.286881* (0.08433) [-3.40195]
IMP(-3)	-0.052363 (0.04181) [-1.25243]	1.800008 (9.99383) [0.18011]	-0.011928 (0.05217) [-0.22865]	0.055977 (0.05482) [1.02113]
C	0.603022 (0.74899) [0.80512]	-7.070582 (179.034) [-0.03949]	0.427513 (0.93454) [0.45746]	1.063310 (0.98204) [1.08275]
R-squared	0.979626	0.995576	0.971003	0.970230
Adj. R-squared	0.978885	0.995415	0.969949	0.969147
Sum sq. resids	7530.935	4.30E+08	11724.63	12946.72
S.E. equation	4.777135	1141.903	5.960636	6.263584
F-statistic	1322.250	6187.932	920.8834	896.2450
Log likelihood	-1016.467	-2894.944	-1092.385	-1109.390
Akaike AIC	6.002723	16.95594	6.445395	6.544546
Schwarz SC	6.148176	17.10140	6.590849	6.689999

Mean dependent	70.89433	28552.26	60.38219	79.81820
S.D. dependent	32.87546	16863.29	34.38445	35.65960

Note: ** indicates significance at 5%

$$INF = 0.924*INF(-1) - 0.055*INF(-2) + 0.126*INF(-3) + 0.0003*EXR(-1) - 0.0005*EXR(-2) + 0.0002*EXR(-3) - 0.032*IMP(-1) + 0.075*IMP(-2) - 0.052*IMP(-3) - 0.015*COP(-1) + 0.024*COP(-2) - 0.009*COP(-3) + 0.603$$

$$EXR = 14.839*INF(-1) + 0.275*INF(-2) - 13.224*INF(-3) + 1.160*EXR(-1) + 0.098*EXR(-2) - 0.274*EXR(-3) - 14.038*IMP(-1) + 13.636*IMP(-2) + 1.800*IMP(-3) + 29.115*COP(-1) - 20.756*COP(-2) - 3.969*COP(-3) - 7.071$$

$$IMP = 0.066*INF(-1) + 0.051*INF(-2) - 0.091*INF(-3) + 0.0002*EXR(-1) + 0.0004*EXR(-2) - 0.0005*EXR(-3) + 1.188*IMP(-1) - 0.287*IMP(-2) + 0.056*IMP(-3) + 0.011*COP(-1) + 0.048*COP(-2) - 0.089*COP(-3) + 1.063$$

$$COP = 0.031*INF(-1) - 0.090*INF(-2) + 0.059*INF(-3) - 2.019*EXR(-1) + 0.0003*EXR(-2) - 0.0002*EXR(-3) - 0.066*IMP(-1) + 0.091*IMP(-2) - 0.012*IMP(-3) + 1.266*COP(-1) - 0.344*COP(-2) + 0.032*COP(-3) + 0.428$$

Table 6: Estimation results for the residual serial correlation VAR test

Lag	LRE* stat	Df	Prob.	Rao F-stat	Df	Prob.
1	12.66918	16	0.6968	0.791280	(16, 987.4)	0.6968
2	39.19034	32	0.1785	1.229382	(32, 1178.0)	0.1786
3	56.87059	48	0.1783	1.189912	(48, 1215.5)	0.1784

Inverse Roots of AR Characteristic Polynomial

Figure 3: Results for VAR Inverse Roots of AR Characteristic Polynomial

The stability of a VAR model can be obtained from Figure 3.

Table 7: Results of the ARDL bounds test

Test Statistic	Value	Significance	I(0)	I(1)
Asymptotic: n=1000				
F-statistic	0.3962	10%	2.72	3.77
K		5%	3.23	4.35
		2.5%	3.69	4.89
		1%	4.29	5.61

Figure 4: ARDL (3, 0, 0, 0) Criteria Graph. Exogenous variable: INF

Figure 5: ARDL (3, 2, 2, 1) criteria graph. Exogenous variable: EXR

Figure 6: ARDL (2, 3, 0, 1) Criteria Graph. Exogenous variable: IMP

Figure 7: ARDL (2, 0, 1, 1) Criteria Graph. Exogenous Variable: COP

Table 8: Results for the ARDL (3, 0, 0, 0) short-run estimate, exogenous variable: INF

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(INF(-1))	-0.079585	0.053343	-1.491953	0.1366
D(INF(-2))	-0.119510	0.053353	-2.239994	0.0257**
CointEq(-1)*	-0.005197	0.002906	-1.788276	0.0746
R-squared	0.024049	Mean dependent var		0.266787
Adjusted R-squared	0.018375	S.D. dependent var		4.752209
S.E. of the regression	4.708346	Akaike infocriterion		5.945158
Sum squared resid	7625.972	Schwarz criterion		5.978438
Log likelihood	-1028.485	Hannan-Quinn criter.		5.958409
Durbin-Watson stat	2.017549			

Note: ** indicates significance at 5%

Table 8 shows the inflation rate interplay with only lag one of the inflation rates

Table 9: Results for ARDL (3, 2, 2, 1) Short-Run Estimate, Dep Variable: EXR

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-68.0119	82.6834	-0.8225	0.4113
D(EXR(-1))	0.1328	0.0492	2.6948	0.0074**
D(EXR(-2))	0.2690	0.0488	5.5068	0.0000**
D(IMP)	16.0199	9.8212	1.6310	0.1038
D(IMP(-1))	-15.6418	9.7907	-1.5976	0.1111
D(COP)	24.9388	10.4655	2.3829	0.0177**
D(COP(-1))	19.0952	10.7598	1.7746	0.0769
D(INF)	-17.4060	12.9537	-1.3437	0.1800
CointEq(-1)*	-0.01767	0.0075	-2.3342	0.0202**
R-squared	0.186239	Mean dependent var		118.5246

Adjusted R-squared	0.166806	S.D. dependent var	1248.073
S.E. of the regression	1139.235	Akaike infocriterion	16.93992
Sum squared resid	4.35E+08	Schwarz criterion	17.04040
Log likelihood	-2904.665	Hannan-Quinn criter.	16.97994
F-statistic	9.583590	Durbin-Watson stat	1.879218
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Note: ** indicates significance at 5%

Table 10: Results for ARDL (2, 3, 0, 1) Short-Run Estimate, Exogenous Variable: IMP

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.2312	0.4260	2.8902	0.0041**
D(IMP(-1))	0.2304	0.0515	4.4700	0.0000**
D(COP)	-0.1181	0.0560	-2.1075	0.0358**
D(COP(-1))	0.0703	0.0588	1.1943	0.2332
D(COP(-2))	0.1002	0.0571	1.7530	0.0805
D(EXR)	0.0005	0.0002	2.1410	0.0330**
CointEq(-1)*	-0.0471	0.0121	-3.8883	0.0001
R-squared	0.117402	Mean dependent var		0.332691
Adjusted R-squared	0.101781	S.D. dependent var		6.506904
S.E. of the regression	6.166882	Akaike infocriterion		6.496287
Sum squared resid	12892.32	Schwarz criterion		6.574106
Log likelihood	-1116.858	Hannan-Quinn criter.		6.527275
F-statistic	7.515537	Durbin-Watson stat		1.977829
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Note: *significant at 5%

Table 11: Results for ARDL (2, 0, 1, 1) Short-Run Estimate, Exogenous Variable: COP

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.546632	0.330207	1.655423	0.0988
D(COP(-1))	0.294549	0.051830	5.682954	0.0000**
D(EXR)	0.000588	0.000248	2.368678	0.0184**
D(IMP)	-0.119507	0.048482	-2.464985	0.0142**
CointEq(-1)*	-0.054250	0.015050	-3.604766	0.0004
R-squared	0.134810	Mean dependent var		0.295994
Adjusted R-squared	0.124691	S.D. dependent var		6.231881
S.E. of the regression	5.830419	Akaike info criterion		6.378359
Sum squared resid	11625.88	Schwarz criterion		6.433825
Log likelihood	-1101.645	Hannan-Quinn criter.		6.400444
F-statistic	13.32228	Durbin-Watson stat		1.988441
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Asterisks (**) indicate significance at 5%

Table 12: Results of the serial correlation LM test for the ARDL (3, 0, 0, 0) model

F-statistic	0.312025	Prob. F(3,337)	0.8167
Obs*R-squared	0.961183	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.8106

Figure 8: Results of the recursive CUSUM test for ARDL (3, 0, 0, 0)

Table 13: Results of the serial correlation LM test for the ARDL (3, 2, 2, 1) model

F-statistic	1.768694	Prob. F(11,332)	0.0583
Obs*R-squared	19.04291	Prob. Chi-Square(11)	0.0603

Figure 9: Result of the recursive CUSUM test for ARDL (3, 2, 2, 1)

Table 14: Results of the serial correlation LM test for ARDL (2, 3, 0, 1) Model

F-statistic	0.680475	Prob. F(3,333)	0.5645
Obs*R-squared	2.108195	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.5503

Figure 10: Results of the recursive CUSUM test for ARDL (2, 3, 0, 1)

Table 15: Results of the serial correlation LM test for the ARDL (2, 0, 1, 1) model

F-statistic	0.839837	Prob. F(3,336)	0.4728
Obs*R-squared	2.582629	Prob. Chi-Square (3)	0.4605

Figure 11: Results of the recursive CUSUM test for ARDL (2, 0, 1, 1)

4. Discussion of the Results

Preliminary Investigation

According to the Jarque-Bera test (Table 1), the probability values for all four macroeconomic variables (INF, EXR, IMP, and COP) are less than 0.05. This indicates that the data are not normally distributed, as the null hypothesis for normality is rejected for each variable, which is consistent with the findings of Uyanto et al. (2022).

The results of the unit root test, detailed in Table 2, indicate that inflation (INF) is stationary at the level. The ADF and PP test statistics significantly exceed their critical values in absolute terms, with probability values of 0.0000 leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Conversely, the exchange rate (EXR), import (IMP), and crude oil price (COP) were found to be non-stationary in their level forms. However, these variables achieved stationarity after the first differencing because their respective test statistics surpass their critical values and are supported by probability values below the 5% significance threshold. The lag

order is selected based on the Akaike Information Criteria (AIC), and from Table 3, the lag order criterion chosen is lag 3 with AIC (35.86559), which is the best fit for the model.

The results of the Johansen cointegration test in Table 4 indicate that the null hypothesis of no cointegration cannot be rejected because the trace statistics consistently fall below the 0.5% critical values. This finding is further supported by the ARDL bound test in Table 7, where the calculated F-statistics [0.396248] is lower than both the I (0) and I (1) critical values at the 5% significance level. Consequently, no evidence of a long-run relationship between the variables was found.

The Evolution of the Variables:

Visual analysis of the INF, EXR, IMP, and COP variables in Figure 1 indicates a significant rise and fluctuation throughout the study period, necessitating data de-trending. Figure 2 presents the different versions of EXR, IMP, and COP; however, INF remained stationary in its original form and did not require differencing. The plots in Figure 2 confirm stationarity, as the variables oscillate around the origin.

Interplay between Inflation Rate, Exchange Rate, Import, and Crude Oil Price Using VAR Model

The results in Table 5 show self-persistence in the inflation equation. Inflation is highly influenced by its first lag (INF (-1)) and third lag (INF (-3)). The coefficients were 0.924 and 0.126, with a massive t-statistic of 16.89 and an average t-statistic of 2.28, respectively, revealing that inflation is very persistent. In the exchange rate equation, the exchange rate is strongly driven by its own first lag (EXR (-1)) and third lag (EXR (-3)), with coefficients of 1.16 and 0.28, respectively, and a very high t-statistic of 22.03 and 5.51, respectively. The exchange rate is influenced by external influence, as observed in the first lag (COP (-1)). Most lags do not significantly impact the COP in the COP equation. However, COP has a significant influence on its own first lag with a coefficient of 1.27 and a t-statistic of 22.7. In the IMP equation, the coefficient of IMP (-1) is 1.187 with a very high t-statistic of 21.60. This means that imports from the previous period are a very strong predictor of imports in the current period (positive momentum). The second lag IMP (-2) with (-0.286) coefficient is also significant, indicating a corrective or mean-reverting effect after two periods. All four vector autoregressive models have very high R-square, INF (0.979), EXR (0.996), COP (0.971), and IMP (0.970), indicating strong explanatory power.

Interplay between the Inflation Rate, Exchange Rate, Import, and Crude Oil Price Using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model

Table 8 presents the short-run estimates of an ARDL (3, 0, 0, 0) specification with inflation as the dependent variable. The ECT coefficient bears the expected negative sign, confirming a convergence toward long-run equilibrium at a speed of 0.0052%. The R-square of approximately 2.4% is extremely low, indicating that the lagged changes in inflation and the error correction term explain only a tiny fraction of the variation in current inflation. The coefficient of D (INF (-2)) is -0.119 with a p-value of 0.0257. There is a significant negative short-run relationship between inflation two periods ago and current inflation.

Considering the ARDL (3,2,2,1) model highlighted in Table 9, the model explains approximately 18.6% variation in the change in EXR. Notably, the ECT is negative and significant (-0.017, $p < 0.05$), confirming an adjustment speed of 1.77%. The coefficients of the lagged-dependent variables EXR (-1) (0.1328) and EXR (-2) (0.2690) are both positive and highly significant. This shows momentum in the exchange rate, as a

change in the previous two periods positively influences the current change. The COP also has a positive coefficient (24.93) and is statistically significant ($p < 0.177$).

A cursory look at the ARDL (2, 3, 0, 1) model in Table 10 exposes approximately 11.7% of the variation in the change in IMP explained by this short-run model. The immediate change in COP and EXR with respective coefficients (-0.1181 and 0.0005) has a significant short-run impact on IMP even though the magnitude is very small. In a similar development, if IMP rose by 23% in the last period, they are likely to rise again in this period. Table 11 presents the outputs of ARDL (2, 0, 1, 1) and shows how changes in the independent variable (EXR and IMP) affect the change in the dependent variable. Unlike the VAR model, the ARDL estimations show substantially low R-square values, i.e., ARDL (3,0,0,0) 0.024, ARDL (3,2,2,1) 0.186, ARDL (2,3,0,1) 0.117, and ARDL (2,0,1,1) 0.135, showing weaker explanatory power.

Evaluation of vector autoregressive and autoregressive distributed lag models

Feature	VAR	ARDL
System View	Treats all variables as endogenous	Treats one variable as dependent and others as exogenous
Complexity	Captures complex lags like INF (-1) and INF (-3) simultaneously	Simplifies to a specific lag, e.g., INF (-2)
R-Square	Has a much higher fit ($R^2=0.978$), indicating that it captures the underlying data structure far more effectively than ARDL.	This model only explains approximately 21% of the variation, which is low.
Major Impact	Significant impact of COP on EXR (29.11)	A similar but lower impact (24.93)

In summary, the vector autoregressive model is a superior choice for these data. The high R^2 and widespread significance of the results indicate that the variables are deeply interconnected. The VAR model coefficients are highly significant predictors of example COP (-1) 29.11. This implies strong feedback loops where variables are endogenous. The VAR model captures more complex lags than the ARDL model.

Post-estimation test:

Some diagnostic tests were conducted, including the serial correlation LM test, cumulative sum test, and the inverse root AR polynomial. The results in Tables 6, 12, 13, 14, and 15 and Figures 3, 8, 9, 10, and 11 show that all the models passed the post-estimation test. This is in line with the work of Ejukwa et al. (2023) on auto-regressive distributed lag modeling of macroeconomic indices in Nigeria, who used the CUSUM test to test for model stability of macroeconomic variables.

Limitations of the Study

Some limitations encountered in this study are as follows:

- i. There is no systematic study of research methodology before undertaking a research project; this is due to the lack of scientific training in research methodology.
- ii. There is also the difficulty of timely availability of published data from various government and other agencies.

i. Financial constraints also played a part in limiting the success of this research.

Conclusion

Preliminary analysis of the study variables revealed distinct differences in their statistical properties. Although EXR, IMP, and COP initially exhibited significant rising trends and fluctuations that required differencing to achieve stationarity, INF was found to be inherently stationary in its original form. Ultimately, all variables were successfully transformed through the de-trending process to oscillate around the origin. The estimation of the VAR model revealed insights into short-term dynamics only among key economic variables, supported by stable outcomes consistent with previous studies. Meanwhile, the ARDL model estimation underscored the significance of auto-correlation effects in fluctuating economic variables, providing detailed insights into short-run impacts and emphasizing the interconnection of economic indicators. In addition, changes in IMP and EXR significantly impact the dependent variables in the short-run. The study concluded that only a short-run relationship existed among the variables, with the VAR model being more suitable (high R-square) for studying short-run relationships among interacting macroeconomic variables. A strong link exists between the four variables and their lags in both the VAR and ARDL model estimates.

Recommendation of the study

The study recommends the following:

- i. Since short-run relationships exist among the variables, policymakers should focus on tactical, immediate interventions rather than relying on long-term structural shifts.
- ii. The analysis highlights that changes in import (IMP) and exchange rate (EXR) significantly impact dependent variables. Regulatory bodies should implement a hedging strategy to manage fluctuations in these two areas.
- iii. Different economic indicators react differently to market shocks, as revealed by the inherently stationary nature of the inflation rate as opposed to the exchange rate, crude oil price, and imports. Therefore, the analyst should account for variable-specific volatility.

Contribution to knowledge

Based on the findings of this study, the following gaps have been identified:

- i. For the period studied, shocks to exchange rate (EXR) or import (IMP) do not have permanent, long-lasting structural impacts on the system, but instead require immediate, tactical policy response.
- ii. This study contributes to the literature by demonstrating the superiority of the VAR model over the ARDL model for this specific dataset.
- iii. By identifying imports and exchange rate as high-impact drivers, this study highlights that these two variables are the most volatile and influential in the immediate term.

Summary

Initial analysis revealed that while EXR, IMP, and COP required transformation to achieve stationarity, INF was stationary in its original state. This study employed vector autoregressive and autoregressive distributed lag models to explore short-term economic fluctuations. The results indicated that IMP and EXR significantly influenced the dependent variables in the short run. Given its higher R^2 value, the VAR model

was deemed more effective for capturing the strong interconnection between these variables and their lags. Tactical immediate intervention is recommended because of the short-term interaction among the variables.

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